

HOW THE SPRAYING OF GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS CHANGES MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER?

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ABSTRACT

Nanofillers have been proposed as an effective mechanism to improve the properties of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP). The present research work describes the fabrication and testing of the graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) reinforced CFRP laminate. Nanofillers solution was deposited on the unidirectional carbon fibre fabric using a spraying technique to reinforce the interfacial and interlaminar properties of CFRP. Before spraying process, different types of solvent (ethanol, methanol, acetone) and surfactant (PVP, CTAB) were tested to obtain a well-dispersed and stable solution. Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) solution was deposited using an airbrush. Control and GNPs sprayed laminate were manufactured and tested in three-point bending and short beam tests. Small improvement (~2%) in 0° flexural modulus and 90° flexural strength properties was observed. It was identified that adhesion of the GNPs coating to the fabric plays an important role. Reasons for the weak adhesion between GNPs and fabric were identified, and recommendations for the process improvement were provided. This spraying method shows good potential to be scaled up at the industrial level and allows for better control of the amount and location of nanofillers applied in the composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are widely used in many industries, including automotive, aerospace and marine, due to their superior mechanical properties and design flexibility [1]. CFRP laminate can be created by laying up several sheets of carbon fibre fabric or prepreg to cure at certain temperature. These CFRP laminates feature favourable in-plane properties [2]; however, their out-of-plane properties suffer from relatively low delamination resistance and low interlaminar shear strength. Failure of these laminates, occurring to the matrix-dominated interlaminar region, is primarily caused by the brittle nature of the epoxy. Researchers constantly endeavour to improve out-of-plane properties of laminates by transverse stitching [3], pinning [4], interleaving [5–7] or introducing a certain amount of nanofillers [8–13]. The latter method combines nano- and micro-scales' reinforcement, creating so-called multiscale or nano-engineered laminates.

Owing to their excellent mechanical properties [14,15], nanofillers such as graphene or carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been used to enhance properties of CFRP laminates. One way to produce multiscale CFRPs is to mix the nanofillers with the matrix. This approach aims to create a homogeneous distribution of nanofillers in epoxy resin, which is achieved by an appropriate combination of material (solvent, nanofillers, low viscosity resin), processing technique (ultrasonic sonication, magnetic stirring, roller milling) and other parameters (mixing time, temperature) [9,16–18]. Quan et al. [18] reported a 26% and 170% increase in mode I and mode II fracture energy of CFRPs at the addition of 1% MWCNTs to the resin. The volume fraction of nanofillers is usually kept low because the introduction of nanofillers will dramatically increase the viscosity of epoxy, which in turns causes the manufacturing difficulty and agglomeration of nanofillers.

An alternative method is to apply nanofillers on the fibre surface directly by dip coating [19,20], electrophoretic deposition [21] or chemical grafting [22]. This technique creates nanofillers-reinforced fibre-matrix interphase. Chen et al. [23] achieved a 60% increase in interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) for CFRP when dip-coated with 0.5 wt% of silanized graphene oxide (GO). Qin et al. [20] applied

graphene nanoplatelet (GNP) to reinforce CFRP and observed a 19% improvement in ILSS and an 82% increase in 90° flexural strength. Deng et al. [21] deposited GO on the carbon fibre and reported a 55% enhancement in ILSS. Although these have demonstrated the enhancement of out-of-plane properties of CFRP laminates, it is difficult to control the location of nanofillers reinforcement.

More recently, spraying technique to introduce CNTs [8,12,24], GNPs [25] or a mixture of CNTs and GO [26] have drawn increasing attention. This method sprays nanofillers solution through the air onto the material surface. Zhang et al. [8] reported a 47 % increase in interlaminar fracture toughness at 0.047 wt% of CNTs sprayed on woven carbon fibre prepreg. Rodriguez-Gonzalez [26] investigated the synergistic effects of the MWCNTs/GO sprayed at the midplane of the CFRP laminate. The highest improvement of 17% and 14 % improvement in mode I and mode II strain energy release was reported for the mixture of MWCNTs/GO. Recently, Wang and Cai [31] sprayed 0.3wt% of GNPs on carbon fibre and manufactured composites using vacuum-assisted resin infusion. A 24.5% improvement in ILSS was reported due to the addition of GNPs. Promising results on spraying nanofillers motivated the authors to investigate the influence of spraying nanofillers on the carbon fibre fabric on mechanical properties of CFRP laminates.

In this study, an appropriate combination of solvent and surfactant were firstly found to prepare nanofillers solution. Spraying method of GNPs solution directly on carbon fibre surface was trialled. The nanofillers solution usually consists of nanofillers and solvent. Here epoxy/hardener was purposely added to the spraying solution to assist the bonding of the coating to carbon fibre [20]. Mechanical properties of the CFRP laminates, including flexural modulus, strength and interlaminar shear strength were investigated and compared with untreated samples.

2 METHODS

2.1 Materials

Unidirectional carbon fibre fabric (Pyrofil TR50S 15K) and IN2 epoxy resin were purchased from Easy Composite (Longton, UK). The thickness and weight of the single layer of fabric are 0.22 mm and 250 g/m², respectively. The carbon fibre has a tensile strength of 5 GPa, a tensile modulus of 240 GPa, the density of 1.82 g/cm³, and a diameter of 7 μm. The IN2 is a high performance, ultra-low viscosity resin, which is mixed with a slow hardener AT30. The mixing ratio of resin to hardener is 100:30. This mixture has a pot life around 80 - 100 minutes and a low viscosity of 200 - 450 mPa.s at 20°C. Optimal curing time of this epoxy is 7 days at 25°C. The maximum Tg temperature of the cured resin is 98 °C. GNPs (xGNP Graphene Nanoplatelet – Grade C750) have a thickness of a few nm, the surface area of 750 m²/g, and bulk density of 0.2-0.4 g/mL. Absolute ethanol, methanol and acetone (Fisher Chemicals, Loughborough, UK) acted as solvents for the spraying solution.

2.2 Preparation and spraying GNPs solution

Before the spraying process, it is essential to obtain a stable well-dispersed GNPs solution. Given a large amount of the solvent is required for the process, a cheap and environmental alternative solvent is preferred. Solvents such as acetone, methanol and ethanol along with two surfactants: cationic CTAB (Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) and non-ionic Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) were tested. The powder surfactant was firstly diluted in distilled water at a concentration 20g/L. The same amount of nanofillers was then added in for the purpose of comparison. The solution was mixed for 30 minutes using magnetic stirrer (IKA C-Mag HS 7) followed by another five minutes in the ultrasonic bath. Solutions were inspected at two-time points: immediately after mixing and 48 hours later. The solution with the best dispersion was selected for the spraying process. Both methanol and ethanol with the addition of PVP were found to disperse GNPs well. This is in agreement with previous findings [12, 24, 27]. Because methanol is toxic, ethanol was finally selected for the spraying process.

The solution was prepared similarly to the procedure reported elsewhere [20], but N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) was replaced by a solution of ethanol and deionised water in weight ratio 7:3 [28]. To achieve 0.5 wt% of GNPs in the CFRP laminate, 35 ml of ethanol was mixed with 15 ml of deionized water, then 0.5 grams of GNPs and 0.3 ml of PVP were added to the solution. The solution was mixed for 30 minutes using magnetic stirrer followed by the ultrasonic bath for 5 minutes. 0.1 gram of hardener

and 0.7 gram of epoxy resin was later added to the mixture. The solution was further mixed for 30 minutes with magnetic stirring and 5 minutes using an ultrasonic bath. The prepared nanofillers solution was sprayed on both sides of each ply of fabric (see Fig. 1). Dual action High-Performance C Plus airbrush (Iwata Japan) was connected to the in-house compressor. The distance between nozzle and fabric during the spraying process was kept at 20 cm. Because a small amount of the hardener and epoxy were added, the solution viscosity increased with time. To avoid too high viscosity, we prepared the solution in 3 batches sequentially. Each batch was adequate to spray 3 or 4 plies of fabric. In total 10 layers of fabric were sprayed. The total weight of the sprayed graphene was approximately 1.5 grams. The coated fabric was later placed in the oven for 3 hours at 60° to evaporate the solvent (Figure 1b).

Figure 1: Preparation of GNPs sprayed carbon fibre fabric.

2.3 Manufacturing CFRP laminate

A unidirectional laminate was made of ten plies of GNPs-reinforced fabrics. Sprayed and control laminates were manufactured using the same wet lay-up method. Epoxy resin and hardener measured with the ratio of 100:30 were mixed using a spatula for 2 minutes. The mixture was degassed using a vacuum chamber at 1 bar for 20 minutes to remove trapped air caused by the mixing process (Fig. 2a). During the wet lay-up, the aluminium plate was covered with a layer of resin using a brush, then the first layer of fabric was placed on it. The pressure was applied by a roller to impregnate the fabric and remove the air. Then, more resin was brushed to cover the existing layer, and the second ply was laid down along the same carbon fibre direction. Subsequently, each layer of fabric was impregnated using hand brush and roller (Fig. 2b). On the 10th layer, peel ply was applied, followed by perforated release film and fabric breather. Both panels were cured using vacuum bagging technique under 1.0 bar pressure in the room temperature, according to curing specification of resin. The thickness of cured reference and sprayed panels were 2.51±0.04mm and 2.74 ±0.03mm, respectively.

2.4 Mechanical testing

Three-point bending test was conducted using the universal tensile machine (Tinus Olsen) to measure flexural modulus and strength of samples. According to BS EN ISO 14125 [29], cross-head loading speed was 2 mm/min. The diameter of the supports and loading cell were 10 mm, and the span length between two supports was 80 mm. Samples of dimensions 100mm x 15 mm x 2 mm from both types of laminates were compared in 0° and 90°. Flexural strength (σ_f) and flexural modulus (E_f) were calculated using as follows:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3F_{max} L}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

$$E_f = \frac{L^3}{4bh^3} \left(\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s} \right) \quad (2)$$

where F_{max} is the maximum load in Newton and $\Delta F/\Delta s$ is the slope of the linear portion of the force displacement graph, L [mm] is the length, b [mm] the width of the specimen, and h [mm] its thickness.

Short beam test was performed according to BS EN ISO 14130 [30] with the loading speed of 1 mm/min. Samples size was 22mm x 15 mm x 2mm for both control and sprayed laminates. The ratio of the span to thickness was set 7:1. Apparent interlaminar shear stress τ (MPa) was calculated from SBT results in the following formula:

$$\tau = \frac{3}{4} \frac{F_{max}}{bh} \quad (3)$$

where F_{max} [N] is the maximum load in the short beam test.

Figure 2: Manufacturing process of CFRP laminates a) degassing resin, b) impregnation carbon fibre with resin, c) vacuum bagging curing.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Flexural properties

Five samples from each group of specimens were subjected to a three-point bending test. Table 1 presents the size information of samples and obtained experimental results. Two types of laminates in the presence/absence of GNPs nanofillers were wet laid-up. Control CFRP material is simply carbon fibre impregnated with resin. In the case of CFRP+GNPs, approximately 0.5 wt% of GNPs was applied to fibres by a spraying process. Note that all values were calculated according to the actual thickness of the laminate. Table 1 showed the increase of thickness of the laminate due to the introduction of GNPs during the spraying process. Adding GNPs increased average breaking force (F_{max}) by 33.4 N and 7 N for 0° and 90° CFRP laminates respectively compared to control samples. The average flexural modulus for 0° unidirectional CFRP increased from 96.6 GPa to 97.38 GPa due to the presence of GNPs. This enhancement corresponds to approximately 1%. On the other hand, flexural strength, slightly decrease from 665.2 to 632.2 MPa. In the case of 90° specimens, a slight decrease of flexural modulus was observed for the samples with sprayed GNPs. On the other hand, the flexural strength changed little from 49.05 to 49.67 MPa.

Laminate ID	UD 0° (Control CFRP)	UD 0° (CFRP+GNPs)	UD 90° (Control CFRP)	UD 90° (CFRP+GNPs)
Length (mm)	102±0.4	100.9±0.44	101.3±1.3	100.7±0.44
Width (mm)	14.3±0.16	14.38±0.09	14.86±0.1	14.43±0.04
Height (mm)	2.55±0.1	2.74±0.11	2.51±0.03	2.71±0.05
F_{max} (N)	513.0±36	546.4±78	40.0±2	47.0±4
E_f (GPa)	96.6±4.5	97.38±2.5	6.05±0.2	5.6±0.6
σ_f (MPa)	665.2±8.2	632.2±24.6	49.04±2.2	49.67±4.2

Table 1: Comparison of 0° and 90° flexural properties of the unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced laminate (control CFRP and CFRP reinforced GNPs).

3.2 Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)

Short beam test (SBT) was used to determine interlaminar shear properties for 0° laminate samples. The principle of SBT is the same as the three-point bending test except for the difference in the beam dimensions. Apparent interlaminar shear strength was calculated according to equation (3). The interlaminar shear strength was deemed valid only when the sample failed in the pure shear mode. However, samples might fail in other modes such as tensile, compressive or plastic deformation. After a couple of trial tests, the length-thickness ratio of 7:1 was adopted to achieve pure shear failure mode. Representative load-displacement curves of short-beam tested samples are shown in Fig.3 where red colour curves represent the CFRP reinforced with GNPs and black ones for pure CFRP as control. CFRP laminate sprayed with GNPs showed a 126 N higher shearing force than control (see Table 2). The average ILSS for pure CFRP amounted to 35.8 MPa. The addition of the GNPs caused a small decrease of 0.9 MPa in ILSS corresponding to around 2.5 % of change. This decrease was related to the increased thickness (~0.19 mm) of the laminate sprayed with nanofillers. The deviations in thickness resulted from manufacturing technique and the introduction of GNPs.

Figure 3: Load-displacement curve of short beam test results.

Laminate	UD 0° (Control CFRP)	UD 0° (CFRP+GNPs)
Span (mm)	17	17
F_{max} (N)	1710 ±106	1836±53
τ (MPa)	35.8±2.1	34.9±1.2

Table 2: Comparison of interlaminar shear properties unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced laminate (control CFRP and CFRP reinforced with GNPs).

4 DISCUSSION

Spraying of GNPs/epoxy/ethanol solution directly on carbon fibre surface was trialled to make use of a GNPs reinforced interphase. The nanofillers solution usually consists of nanofillers and solvent. Here epoxy/hardener was purposely added to the spraying solution to assist the bonding of the coating to carbon fibres [20]. The recommended weight ratio of the hardener as given by supplier was intentionally reduced by 50% (epoxy to resin ratio 100:15) in the spraying solution. The concentration of nanofillers in the published results varies from up to 10 wt% [19]. The optimal concentration of the GNPs in the coating was selected as 0.5 wt% in CFRP, which is similar to one of the recent work [31].

To examine the mechanical performance of GNPs reinforced CFRP, three-point bending test and short beam tests were performed. The introduction of GNPs increased some flexural and interlaminar properties of CFRP samples. The extent of enhancement is smaller than expected. Flexural modulus in 0° GNPs sprayed laminate, and flexural strength of 90° GNPs sprayed laminate increase a little (1.2%). A small decrease in some properties, i.e. interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was also observed. In this work, a similar value of ILSS for control CFRP (35.8 MPa) was obtained compared to published results (36.7 MPa) [31]. Contrarily, the same study reported a 19% increase in ILSS for CFRP sprayed with 0.5wt% GNPs. Here, the decrease in the properties is correlated with the increased thickness of the laminate. A small increase in the laminate thickness is expected due to the spraying process, but that increase was not quantified in [31].

One of the possible reasons for small improvement was adhesion of the GNPs coating to fibres surface. The weak adhesion of the GNPs coating to carbon fibre process was observed at the time of samples preparation. During the wet lay-up process, when the resin was applied with brush and roller, some of the weakly bonded nanofillers were taken away from the fibre surface. This was confirmed by the change of resin colour from transparent to black (Fig. 2c), suggesting that nanofillers transferred from the fibre surface to the matrix during the wet lay-up. This means that some GNPs were not properly bonded to carbon fibres.

Many factors can cause weak adhesion. One of them could be inappropriate curing conditions of the sprayed fabric. These conditions depend not only on the amount of solvent and nanofillers, epoxy and hardener but also on curing time and temperature. The present curing time was 3 hours in 60 degrees. It was taken from the literature [20], which was designed initially for GNPs/Epon 828/mPDA/NMP solutions. The optimal curing conditions for sprayed fabric at a given composition of the solution needs to be found in order to gain stronger bonding with carbon fibre.

Another possible issue of the bad adhesion could be commercial sizing on the 'as-received' carbon fibre fabric. This sizing is usually designed to improve the wettability of fibres for resin impregnation, which could have a negative effect on the ability of GNPs solution bonding to the surface. Prior to the coating process, de-sizing carbon fibre was used to remove the commercial sizing, which is believed to improve adhesion [20]. In this wet lay-up, the GNPs coated fabric should be carefully brushed with resin, so that the minimum amount of GNPs are carried away. Other laminate manufacturing process such us resin infusion or prepreg manufacturing could also be considered.

The main challenge of all coating processes is to make nano-reinforced interphase of uniform thickness with a homogenous distribution of nanofillers. Spraying method has a huge potential to be scaled up at the industrial level. For the moment, the spraying gun was operated manually. The sample finish is very much dependent on the experience of the operator, which may introduce some non-uniformity of the coating. This can be avoided by the automation of the spraying process, which will advantageously lead to more controllable process conditions. Also, a continuous mixing process before feeding the solution into the spraying gun could be also beneficial. The spraying process is limited to certain types of carbon fibre fabric. Under the same spraying process, the fabric of lower weight per square metre is easier to achieve an even impregnation of carbon fibre by spraying solution. To achieve a better enhancement, the spraying process could also be applied directly to fibre tow, which later can be made in different types of fabric - this challenge is posed by other coating methods as well.

The spraying process has some advantages over other coating methods. For example, a dip coating method requires a large amount of nanofillers solution. When the carbon fibre tow is pulled through the nanofillers solution bath, the amount of the deposited GNPs will be affected by the tow feeding speed. After the deposition process, it is difficult to quantify the concentration of residuals nanofillers in the solution bath. This will make it difficult if not impossible, to prepare the solution of the same GNPs concentration from the “used” solution to achieve a uniform coating. In the case of the spraying process, the desired amount of the solution can be calculated, prepared beforehand and better used in full. The exact amount of nanofillers in the CFRP can be controlled so that the finish will be much easier to repeat.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Spraying method has proven to be an effective technique to create GNPs coating. Some enhancement of mechanical properties was found which, in turns, largely depends on the adhesion between coating and carbon fibre. The optimal curing conditions of sprayed fabric are currently being reviewed.

Spraying method has a considerable potential to be expanded at the industrial level. Automation of this technique will advantageously lead to controllable process conditions, which allow to design and optimise the coating properties. The main challenge of all coating processes is to make nano-reinforced interphase of uniform thickness with a homogenous distribution of nanofillers.

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